

Track Machine Learning in Your Research Domain

Information Extraction from Scientific Publications as a Service

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Abstract

Machine Learning (ML) plays an increasingly central role in research across disciplines. This development is driven by recent advances in AI, especially in large language models (LLMs)[1], which have broadened the accessibility and use of ML-based methods in many fields.[2] Despite the wider availability of ML-based methods, we argue that the awareness of ML usage in research is vital to researchers for two reasons. On the one hand, researcher in all fields need to understand how ML techniques are applied in comparable existing work to use them effectively in their own work; on the other hand, the ML usage information is required to consolidate the research scope and evaluate the research reproducibility and reliability. This awareness and understanding of ML usage includes identifying relevant ML techniques, datasets, tasks and tools related to the specific research. As ML methods become more widespread, structured access to this information becomes essential because manual analysis of ML usage in scholarly literature is time-consuming and does not scale well. To address this, we are developing and evaluating methods and models to automatically extract ML-related information from research publications.

Our joined effort of two NFDI consortia: BERD and NFDI4DataScience will be converted to a service to support researchers of various domains. More specifically, we present a service on top of our extraction models that allows researchers to analyze ML usage in a targeted set of publications, representing their specific research domains, thereby promoting the findability of research artifacts. Researchers can upload their own PDF collections (e.g., a reference lists for ongoing research projects) and receive detailed insights into the use of ML models, datasets, tasks, and methods. This includes highlighted terms within the text and aggregated statistics, helping users understand ML usage both in individual papers and across a research field.

Our extraction pipeline is based on GSAP-NER[3], a named entity recognition model optimized for scientific texts and ML terminology. It uses a fine-grained data model designed to identify specific ML-related entities in context. The model was trained on a manually annotated corpus of 100 research publications, selected from Huggingface model readme files and randomly sampled arXiv papers. Annotation guidelines were developed by domain experts to ensure consistency. The results show that the method is suitable for extracting high-quality structured data for our described use case.

By providing structured access to ML usage, our work enables better discovery and understanding of the methodologies across the research domains, directly supporting research data management goals. The user-facing service allows researchers to define a research field by uploading relevant PDFs. After processing, they can read the papers including highlighted ML-related terms which helps to identify relevant methodological information. Additionally, researcher can access structured statistics about the use of ML models, datasets, tasks, and methods in their selection. References and links mentioned alongside the identified resources are provided, and a feedback loop allows users to suggest corrections or additions. This supports both domain-specific overviews and continuous improvement of the extraction models. Future work will include linking extracted entities to external repositories and research knowledge graphs such as Paper with Code, Huggingface, the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)[4] and NFDI-related Knowledge Graphs[5]. We also plan to enable cross-domain comparisons by using the extracted knowledge of other users. This will provide broader insights into how ML methods are shared and reused in scientific practice.

Resources

- GSAP Project. <https://data.gesis.org/gsap>. Documentation, Video and Prototypes.
- GSAP-NER. <https://github.com/ottowg/gsap-ner>. Code and Data.

Author contributions

Wolfgang Otto: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data Curation, Validation; Writing – Original Draft.

Sharmila Upadhyaya: Conceptualization, Software; Writing – Review & Editing.

Lu Gan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data Curation; Writing – Review & Editing.

Kanishka Silva: Conceptualization; Writing – Review & Editing.

See the [CRedit taxonomy](#) for role definitions.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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